

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391197464>

Sustainable Energy Management in Industrial Wastewater Treatment: A Case Study of a Textile Industry

Conference Paper · April 2025

CITATIONS

0

READS

44

9 authors, including:

Md Shariful Islam Shuvo

Gopalganj Science and Technology University

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Khaled Mohammad Shifullah

Rajshahi University of Engineering and Technology

16 PUBLICATIONS 58 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Sustainable Energy Management in Industrial Wastewater Treatment: A Case Study of a Textile Industry

Nusrat Jahan¹, Md. Shariful Islam Shuvo¹, Muzahada Binta Mukbul², Khaled Mohammad Shifullah Bhuiya^{3,*}, Angkur Saha⁴, Md Mahamudul Hossain Bhuiyan⁵

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Gopalganj Science and Technology University, Gopalganj 8100, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

nusratpromi21@gmail.com, shariful.islam.shuvo25@gmail.com

²Department of Applied Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Noakhali Science and Technology University, Noakhali-3814, Bangladesh. evanaeva2001@gmail.com

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, Rajshahi University of Engineering & Technology, Rajshahi-6204, Bangladesh. kms.bhuiya@gmail.com

⁴Department of Physics, University of Rajshahi, 6205. angkursaha1999@gmail.com

⁵Department of Mechanical Engineering, Bangladesh Army University of Science and Technology, Saidpur cantonment, Nilphamari, 5310. mahamudul_200103002_stud@baust.edu.bd

*Corresponding author: Khaled Mohammad Shifullah Bhuiya

Keywords:

- Energy management;
- Wastewater treatment;
- Textile industry;
- Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP);
- Energy efficiency

Abstract: Effective energy management in industrial wastewater treatment is critical for cost reduction and environmental sustainability. This study examines energy consumption patterns in a textile industry's Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) and evaluates sustainable energy management strategies. Through detailed energy audits, biological oxidation was identified as the most energy-intensive process (27.65% of total consumption), followed by sludge separation (16.98%) and neutralization (11.14%). The study explores energy-saving measures such as Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs), advanced oxidation processes, and wastewater heat recovery systems, demonstrating their potential to reduce energy consumption by up to 30%. Results indicate that optimizing high-energy processes can significantly enhance treatment efficiency while lowering operational costs. This research provides a framework for integrating sustainable energy solutions into industrial wastewater management, contributing to broader environmental and economic benefits in the textile sector.

1. Introduction

The textile industry in Bangladesh plays a crucial role in the national economy, employing over 4 million people, with women constituting the majority of the workforce (Dey et al., 2015). However, the sector is a major contributor to environmental pollution, particularly through the discharge of untreated wastewater into natural water bodies, such as the Turag and Shitalakkhya rivers (Islam et al., 2011). Textile effluents contain high concentrations of organic and inorganic contaminants, including dyes, bleaching agents, heavy metals, and acids (Mostafa, M., 2015). Approximately 20% of global industrial water pollution originates from textile dyeing and finishing processes (Shefa et al., 2024). Effluent Treatment Plants (ETPs) are crucial in mitigating the environmental impact of textile wastewater by treating effluents to meet regulatory standards (Gomes et al., 2024). Energy management within ETPs is essential for enhancing sustainability and reducing operational costs. Strategies such as optimizing chemical dosing, improving aeration efficiency, and implementing energy-efficient technologies, including Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs)

and advanced oxidation processes, can significantly improve treatment performance while minimizing energy consumption (Rafiq et al., 2024). Additionally, recovering thermal energy from wastewater can reduce reliance on conventional energy sources, lowering carbon emissions and operational expenditures.

This study investigates energy consumption in a textile industry’s ETP, identifies energy-intensive stages, and evaluates the effectiveness of sustainable energy management techniques. The primary research question of this work is: How can energy consumption be optimized in a textile industry’s Effluent Treatment Plant while maintaining high treatment efficiency? The findings of this work will contribute to the development of practical strategies for improving energy efficiency while maintaining high treatment performance.

2. Method

This study systematically evaluates energy consumption across various stages of an Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) in a textile industry, identifying opportunities for efficiency improvements. The ETP process involves multiple treatment stages, each with distinct energy requirements, which are assessed to determine areas for potential energy savings. The process, as shown in Figure 1, begins with a bar screen that removes large solid particles to prevent clogging. The wastewater then flows into a collection tank for temporary storage and homogenization before entering the process house for initial processing and monitoring. Next, it moves to the equalization tank, which regulates flow rate and pollutant concentration fluctuations to ensure uniform treatment. In the neutralization stage, the pH is adjusted to an optimal range, followed by chemical coagulation, where coagulants aggregate suspended particles into flocs for easier separation.

Figure 1: Flow chart of the processes in an ETP plant

The water then enters the biological oxidation tank, where microorganisms break down organic pollutants using aeration systems. Further treatment occurs in the flash mixer, where polymers enhance the settling of remaining solids before being transferred to the settling tank, where sludge is separated under pressure. Finally, the clarified water undergoes filtration to remove residual fine particles before being safely discharged.

To assess energy consumption, detailed measurements were conducted at each stage, capturing data on electricity usage, motor and pump capacities, aeration systems, and chemical dosing units. Energy data were collected from operational logs and real-time monitoring, ensuring accuracy through validation with plant engineers and industry benchmarks. The analysis identified high-energy-consuming processes and explored potential efficiency improvements through equipment upgrades, process optimization, and operational modifications.

This study aims to provide actionable recommendations for reducing energy consumption in the ETP while maintaining treatment efficiency. By implementing these strategies, textile industries can enhance sustainability, lower operational costs, and minimize their environmental footprint in wastewater management.

3. Result and Discussions

The collected data are systematically organized in tabular form to enhance clarity and facilitate calculations. Table 1 provides details on the machines used in different processes, including their power rating and power consumption, along with their operating hours (hours/day). The Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) operates for 25 days each month.

Base on the data from Table 1, the energy consumption is calculated from Eq. (1) and represented graphically in figure 2.

$$\text{Energy consumption} = \text{Total operation (h)} \times \text{Total Power (W)} \quad (1)$$

In figure 2, the energy consumption analysis of the Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) is presented, showing the distribution across different treatment stages. The total estimated energy consumption is 47,475 kWh, with biological oxidation being the most energy-intensive process, accounting for 27.65% or 13,125 kWh due to continuous aeration requirements for microbial degradation. Sludge separation accounts for 16.98% or 8,062.5 kWh, and neutralization contributes 11.14% or 5,287.5 kWh, driven by clarifier operations and chemical dosing systems, respectively. Equalization requires 9.08% or 4,312.5 kWh, chemical coagulation consumes 5.21% or 2,475 kWh, filtration accounts for 5.85% or 2,775 kWh, and flash mixing with polymer requires 6.32% or 3,000 kWh, all of which support flow stabilization, solid separation, and enhanced coagulation. The lower energy-consuming stages include bar screening with 3.95% or 1,875 kWh, collection tank operation with 4.27% or 2,025 kWh, and treated water discharge with 3.95% or 1,875 kWh, primarily involving mechanical filtration and pumping. The findings emphasize the need for optimizing high-energy processes through advanced aeration strategies, efficient sludge management, and intelligent process control to enhance overall energy efficiency while maintaining treatment performance.

Form the calculation it is found that among the various processes in the Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP), some stages, such as biological oxidation, sludge separation, and neutralization, are highly energy-intensive due to their reliance on continuous aeration, mechanical pumping, and chemical dosing.

Table 1: Operation hour of machines & Power consumption of each machine

Process	Machine(s)	Specific Power Rating (kW)	Quantity	Total Power Consumption (kWh)	Operation (hours/days)
Bar Screening	Bar Screen	2.0	1	2.0	15
	Conveying System	1.5	2	3.0	15
Collection Tank	Collection Tank (Pumps)	3.0	1	3.0	15
	Agitator	1.2	2	2.4	15
Process House	Transfer Pumps	4.0	1	4.0	15
	Valves	1.5	1	1.5	15
	Flow Regulators	0.8	2	1.6	15
Equalization	Equalization Tank (Mixers)	2.5	1	2.5	15
	Pumps	3.0	3	9.0	15
Neutralization	Chemical Dosing Systems	2.2	3	6.6	15
	Agitators	1.5	5	7.5	15
Chemical Coagulation	Coagulation Tank (Mixer)	2.4	2	4.8	15
	Coagulant Dosing Pumps	1.8	1	1.8	15
Biological Oxidation	Aeration Tank (Aerators)	15.0	1	15.0	15
	Blowers	10.0	2	20.0	15
Flash Mixing with Polymer	Flash Mixer	3.0	1	3.0	15
	Polymer Injection System	2.5	2	5.0	15
Settling and Separation of Sludge	Clarifier (Settling Tank)	3.5	5	17.5	15
	Sludge Pumps	2.0	2	4.0	15
Filtration	Sand Filter	2.2	2	4.4	15
	Activated Carbon Filter (Pumps)	3.0	1	3.0	15
Treated Water Discharge	Discharge Pump	3.0	1	3.0	15
	Pressure Tank	2.0	1	2.0	15

These processes consume a significant portion of the total energy used in wastewater treatment, making them key targets for efficiency improvements. To address this issue, Table 2 presents several proposed techniques aimed at reducing energy consumption in these high-energy processes. By implementing

advanced aeration strategies, optimizing chemical dosing, and upgrading to energy-efficient equipment, substantial energy savings can be achieved without compromising treatment performance. The proposed methods not only lower operational costs but also contribute to sustainable wastewater management by reducing the carbon footprint of industrial effluent treatment.

Figure 2: Breakdown of energy consumption in different process in a month

Table 2: Proposed Energy Reduction Techniques for ETP Processes

Process	Current Energy Consumption (kWh/month)	Percentage of Total Energy Use	Proposed Energy Reduction Techniques	Expected Reduction (%)	References
Biological Oxidation	13,125	27.65%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use fine bubble diffusers instead of coarse bubble diffusers. - Optimize aeration control with dissolved oxygen sensors. - Implement Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs) on blowers. 	20-30%	(Rosso, D.,2008)
Sludge Separation	8,062.5	16.98%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimize sludge pumping schedules. - Utilize gravity-assisted sludge thickening. - Upgrade to energy-efficient pumps. 	15-25%	(Metcalf, & Eddy, 2011)

Process	Current Energy Consumption (kWh/month)	Percentage of Total Energy Use	Proposed Energy Reduction Techniques	Expected Reduction (%)	References
Neutralization	5,287.5	11.14%	- Implement automated chemical dosing based on real-time pH monitoring. - Replace inefficient mechanical mixers with energy-efficient alternatives.	10-20%	(EPA, 2010)

4. Conclusion

This study analyses energy consumption patterns in a textile industry's Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP) and identifies the most energy-intensive processes. The findings indicate that biological oxidation (27.65%), sludge separation (16.98%), and neutralization (11.14%) account for the highest energy usage. By implementing targeted energy management strategies such as fine bubble diffusers, Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs), optimized sludge handling, and automated chemical dosing, energy consumption can be reduced by up to 30%, leading to substantial cost savings and environmental benefits. The findings emphasize the necessity of optimizing high-energy processes through efficient aeration control, process automation, and energy-efficient equipment. Moreover, integrating renewable energy sources such as solar power and wastewater heat recovery can further enhance sustainability. Future research should focus on real-time energy monitoring, advanced process modelling, and the economic feasibility of large-scale implementation to drive sustainable energy practices in industrial wastewater treatment.

References

1. Dey, S., Islam, A., A review on textile wastewater characterization in Bangladesh, *Resources and Environment*. 2015, 5(1); 15–44.
2. Islam, M.M., Mahmud, K., Faruk, O. et al., Textile dyeing industries in Bangladesh for sustainable development, *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development*. 2011, 2(6); 428.
3. Mostafa, M., Waste water treatment in textile industries—the concept and current removal technologies, *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*. 2015, 7(1); 501–525.
4. Shefa, J., Xames, M.D., Hasan, A.A. et al., Feasibility study of common effluent treatment plant for management of industrial wastewater: Case study of Bangladeshi textile industries, *Environmental Quality Management*. 2024, 33(4); 165–178.
5. Gomes, K., Caucci, S., Morris, J. et al., Sustainability transformation in the textile industry—the case of wastewater management, *Business Strategy & Development*. 2024, 7(1); e324.
6. Rafiq, M., Apurba, M.S.H., Khandaker, N.R., Implementing sustainable practices in wastewater treatment and material waste management in the textile and apparel sector of Bangladesh, In 7th International Conference on Civil Engineering for Sustainable Development. 2024.
7. Rosso, D., Stenstrom, M.K., Larson, L.E. et al., Aeration efficiency in wastewater treatment plants: Evaluation and effects of design and operation, *Water Environment Research*. 2008, 80(7); 687–698.
8. Metcalf, & Eddy, Inc., *Wastewater Engineering: Treatment and Reuse*, 5th ed. McGraw-Hill, 2011
9. EPA (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency), 2010. *Energy Efficiency in Water and Wastewater Facilities*, Available in: <https://www.epa.gov/energy/energy-efficiency-water-and-wastewater-facilities> (accessed 30 January 2025).